

THE PROGNOSTIC VALUE OF THE EXPRESSION OF P53 IN SQUAMOUS CELL CERVICAL CARCINOMA

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The actuality of the topic is due to the high prevalence of cervical cancer, its diagnosis mainly at latestages and unsatisfactory treatment results, which requires improvement of screening methods and treatment of patients with this form of the disease.

Objective: To investigate the expression of the cancer protein p53 as a potential prognostic marker for the effectiveness of preoperative chemotherapy, radiation, and combined treatments on cervical cancer during patient examination. The p53 gene is a tumor suppressor gene that functions in normal cells through the simultaneous activity of both alleles. However, a malfunction in the p53 gene can occur due to the loss of one allele or mutation in the other, resulting in overexpression of the cancer protein p53 or the emergence of a mutant form, leading to a loss of its ability to inhibit cell proliferation. This uncontrolled proliferation can lead to tumor cell growth. There is widespread discussion about the prognostic significance of cancer protein p53 in cervical cancer patients. Some foreign studies have not found a clear connection between overexpression of p53 protein (or presence of a mutation in the p53 gene) and clinical course of disease. Others believe that the expression of the mutated cancer protein p53 is responsible for the development of tumors with a poor prognosis.

Materials and methods: the biopsy and surgical material of 40 patients (aged 25 to 70 years) with squamous cell carcinoma of the cervix of the Ib-III stage before and after receiving combined treatment was analyzed. The size of the cervix was compared before and after the treatment (according to the results of ultrasound examination of the pelvic organs). The histological structure of the tumor, the severity of therapeutic pathomorphosis and the expression of cancer protein p53 were determined using Dako monoclonal antibodies (clone DO-7), EnVision TM + Dual Link imaging system and DAB chromogen (Dako). The results of the study: The cervix was enlarged in all cases before the treatment. After the therapy, in 38 out of 40 cases, its volume and size decreased. According to the histological structure, highly differentiated cancers were observed in 6 cases, moderately differentiated cancers in 16, low-grade cancer from small cells in 4 cases and squamous cell carcinoma from large cells

in 12 cases. The degree of therapeutic pathomorphosis in 20 patients was determined as 1-2, in 18 women – 2-3 and in 4 patients – 4. Expression of p53 before therapy was observed in 30 cases (75%). Initially, high expression (in more than 10% of tumor cells) was detected in 22 cases (55%), weak in 8 cases (20%), and p53 was absent in 10 cases (25%). Increased expression after treatment was observed in 22 cases with both an initially high p53 index (14 cases) and in observations with initially weak or absent expression (8 cases). There was a decrease in p53 in 6 cases (4 with an initially high p53, 2 with a low ones). In 6 cases, expression was absent both before and after the therapy. In 6 cases, p53 remained unchanged (2 cases with weak expression, 4 with pronounced expression). In 60% of cases with initially high p53 levels or its enhancement during treatment, therapeutic pathomorphosis was low (1-2 degrees). In 33.3%, the degree of pathomorphosis was regarded as 2-3. In only two cases (6.6%), the degree of pathomorphosis was regarded as 3-4, but at the same time, the intensity of staining of preserved tumor cells after therapy increased and clinically, further progression of the disease with bladder germination and liver metastases was noted in the patient. In all cases with initially low p53 expression, the degree of pathomorphosis was exclusively 1-2. However, in four cases, after the therapy, an increase in the accumulation of p53 was noted (in two – pronounced, in the others – weak). In the observation with a marked increase in expression after treatment, there was also a sharp increase in mitotic activity (up to 25 mitoses in the field of vision). In the case of a slight increase in p53 after therapy, despite a marked regression of the tumor (a decrease in tumor volume by 68%), tumor emboli in the vascular lumen were noted. In another case, multiple tumor emboli were noted, but the accumulation of p53 after therapy was somewhat reduced.

In cases with no expression of cancer protein p53 before treatment, the degree of pathomorphosis was assessed as 1-2 (4 cases) and 2-3 (6 cases). After the therapy, in two cases with the initial absence of p53, very weak expression of the marker appeared. Clinically, in 4 cases, the disease progressed with continued growth in the pelvis. Thus, these cases do not fit into the general idea of the relationship between p53 expression and disease prognosis.

Conclusions: The degree of differentiation of squamous cell carcinoma did not correlate either with the level of expression of cancer protein p53 or with the degree of therapeutic pathomorphosis. The expression of p53 of varying severity in the primary material was observed in 75% of cases. Despite the decrease in the size of the cervix during treatment, a low degree of therapeutic

pathomorphosis was observed in 60% of cases. An increase in the expression level of cancer protein p53, which was accompanied by a low degree of therapeutic pathomorphosis, was noted in 55% of women, and in some cases this was accompanied by a sharp increase in mitotic activity, continued tumor growth, and distant metastasis within 1-2 years after surgery. This pattern was accompanied by a low degree of therapeutic pathomorphosis. In the case of a high degree of pathomorphosis, tumor cells with high expression of cancer protein were preserved. Thus, the expression level of cancer protein p53 may be significant for evaluating the effectiveness of treatment of patients at the preoperative stage.

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